

KNOWLEDGE
WITHOUT
BOUNDARIES

eifl 2024
ANNUAL
REPORT

WHERE WE WORK

In 2024, EIFL worked in partnership with library consortia in 37 countries. We have also run projects in an additional 19 countries where we do not have library consortia.

- **PARTNER COUNTRIES** are countries where we have a formal agreement with the national library consortium. EIFL partner consortia work with all EIFL programmes.
- **PROJECT COUNTRIES** are countries in which we have worked with libraries on specific projects.

WHERE WE WORK

EIFL works in collaboration with libraries in 56 developing and transition countries.

AFRICA Botswana, Côte d'Ivoire, Democratic Republic of Congo, Ethiopia, Ghana, Kenya, Lesotho, Malawi, Namibia, Mozambique, Nigeria, Rwanda, Senegal, South Africa, Tanzania, Uganda, Zambia, Zimbabwe **ASIA PACIFIC** Cambodia, China, Fiji, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Laos, Maldives, Mongolia, Myanmar, Nepal, Thailand, Uzbekistan **EUROPE** Albania, Armenia, Azerbaijan, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Estonia, Georgia, Hungary, Kosovo, Latvia, Lithuania, Moldova, North Macedonia, Poland, Romania, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Ukraine **LATIN AMERICA** Chile, Colombia **MIDDLE EAST & NORTH AFRICA** Palestine, Sudan, Syria.

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**OUR VISION IS A WORLD IN
WHICH ALL PEOPLE HAVE THE
KNOWLEDGE THEY NEED TO
ACHIEVE THEIR FULL POTENTIAL.**

WHO WE ARE

EIFL (Electronic Information for Libraries) is an international not-for-profit organization that works with libraries in developing and transition countries to enable access to knowledge for education, learning, research and sustainable community development.

In 2024, we began implementing a new strategic plan, for the period 2024 - 2026. The plan has three main goals:

To advance a fair and sustainable transition from paywalled to open access content

Major achievements in 2024 —

- By the end of the year, 15 agreements with publishers were in place enabling authors from EIFL partner countries to publish for free or at reduced prices in open access in 2,927 journals. 2,648 articles were published in open access in 2024. Savings in Article Processing Charges (APCs) amounted to US\$4,301,992.
- We contributed to strengthening no-fee (Diamond) open access journal publishing in Africa and Europe. Diamond open access is a scholarly communications model in which journals do not charge fees to either authors or readers—
 - **Africa:** We released the first-ever landscape study of no-fee open access publishing in Africa. After issuing a continent-wide open call for proposals, we awarded grants to 22 no-fee open access journal publishers in nine countries to strengthen their efficiency, quality and sustainability.
 - **Europe:** We contributed to a landscape study of Diamond open access publishing in Europe, and the drafting of standards and quality guidelines for Diamond open access publishing.

To support research, teaching and learning

Major achievements in 2024 —

- We continued to negotiate agreements with publishers for free or affordable pricing for paywalled e-resources. By the end of 2024, 78 commercial e-resources from 25 vendors were available through EIFL, including e-journals, e-books, reference works and aggregated databases covering a broad range of subject areas. EIFL-negotiated agreements saved libraries approximately US\$750 million in subscription fees.
- We advocated for national copyright law reform to encourage the adoption of modern copyright laws that maximize access to content:
 - We participated in copyright law reviews in eight countries: Armenia, Georgia, Malawi, Moldova, South Africa, Thailand, Uganda and Ukraine.
 - We contributed to ending the book famine for persons with print disabilities by supporting ratification and domestication of the Marrakesh Treaty in seven countries: Azerbaijan, Georgia, Kenya, Lesotho, Malawi, Moldova and Uganda.
- We advocated for an enabling policy environment to support open and reproducible research. As a result of our policy work, seven national (Lithuania - 1, Serbia - 1, Slovenia - 2, Ukraine - 3) and two institutional (Serbia, Slovenia) open science policies were adopted.
- We supported the creation and maintenance of open public infrastructures that enable the publication and sharing of research in open access journals and repositories, and helped

to improve the quality of services of over 400 open access journals in Africa and Ukraine and three repositories in Botswana, Georgia and Kenya.

- We strengthened open science training:
 - We built a community of over 60 open science trainers from 16 EIFL partner countries and organized monthly online meetings for exchanging knowledge and training experiences.
 - We supported open science training by co-facilitating two OpenAIRE open science train-the-trainer bootcamps.
- We developed useful new resources for open access and open science training:
 - 'EIFL guide and checklist for researchers and librarians: Choosing a journal for your research';
 - 'EIFL Open Science for Health Sciences Training Programme Outline for librarians and open science trainers';
 - 'EIFL Artificial Intelligence and Open Science Training Programme Outline for librarians and open science trainers';
 - Open science practices handbook and online course (in Ukrainian).

To foster digital transformation of public library services

- We advanced training, facilitation and digital skills of public librarians in Ghana as part of the 'Digital learning @ Ghana public libraries' project:
 - Thirty public librarians and ICT coordinators from 15 regional and branch libraries managed by the Ghana Library Authority

completed four training-of-trainers workshops, enabling them to provide essential digital literacy training to school students and to introduce students to open educational resources.

- By the end of 2024, the trained librarians had conducted 122 outreach visits to schools, engaging 6,966 students in short classes on MS Office applications, graphic design and coding. They had also organized 22 digital literacy workshops in libraries, attracting 804 school students.
- We met with national library authorities and government and private sector stakeholders in Malawi and Zambia to advocate for improving ICT infrastructure in public libraries, and to build partnerships for enhancing digital skills of public librarians in those countries.
- Uganda Communications Commission (UCC) continued to equip public and community libraries with ICT as a result of our previous advocacy efforts with the government (dating back to 2018). In 2024 the UCC equipped 10 more libraries with computers, wireless internet, a printer, a scanner and a photocopier.
- We continued to produce online learning material based on the EIFL-PLIP training curriculum for public librarians, including five more short videos in the EIFL-PLIP 'Small Bites' series.
- To advance innovation in public libraries, we selected three libraries (in Brazil, Lithuania, and Philippines) for the 18th EIFL Public Library Innovation Award. The award was for integration of digital reading and writing to enhance public library services.

DIRECTOR'S REPORT

This year we began implementing our 2024 - 2026 Strategic Plan. Our new Strategic Plan builds on achievements of the previous period, and takes forward our mission of enabling access to knowledge for all.

In the new Strategic Plan, the EIFL Copyright and Libraries Programme shifts its focus to the national level, advocating for the adoption of fair copyright laws that maximize access to content, and implementation of the Marrakesh Treaty which enables access to knowledge for persons with print disabilities. In 2024, we participated in copyright law reviews in 11 countries, and Georgia became the 27th partner country to join the Marrakesh Treaty.

Scholars in our partner countries continue to benefit from the EIFL Licensing Programme's negotiations with publishers for free or affordable access to paywalled content. In 2024, usage of e-resources subscribed by libraries in partner consortia was very good—there were over 10.7 million downloads of full text articles and book chapters.

We are pleased to see an increase in open access publishing by authors in our partner countries as a result of agreements negotiated by our Licensing Programme. These agreements include waivers or discounts of Article Processing Charges (APCs) for publishing articles in hybrid or fully open access journals, making research more accessible and visible.

In November, we celebrated Iryna Kuchma, our Open Access Programme Manager, who won the 2024 Networked Digital Library of Theses and Dissertations (NDLTD) Leadership Award. Iryna's passionate advocacy has contributed to the adoption of hundreds of open access and open science policies that mandate the deposit of research outputs in repositories, with electronic thesis and dissertations being a major content type. In 2024, the EIFL Open Access Programme continued to actively

support open infrastructures that enable the publication and sharing of research results in open access journals and repositories, and to build open science skills.

The main feature article of this report highlights the work of the EIFL Public Library Innovation Programme (EIFL-PLIP) in accelerating digital inclusion in Uganda. Over several years, we worked with the National Library of Uganda, simultaneously improving public librarians' digital and training skills and advocating with the Uganda Communications Commission (UCC) for resourcing of public and community libraries with ICT for public use. By the end of 2024, the UCC had installed computers, wifi, printers, scanners and photocopiers at 39 libraries. In 2024 the UCC earmarked 30 more libraries for their rollout in 2025 and made commitments for further years. Advocacy by EIFL-PLIP and the Kenya National Library Service (KNLS) with the Communications Authority of Kenya in 2016 resulted in similar success, with the installation of computers and the internet for public use in all 61 libraries in the KNLS network at the time. In both Uganda and Kenya, librarians are using the technology to provide community information services and digital skills training in their communities.

Further achievements are detailed in the **Who We Are** section of this report.

Thank you to everyone—our partners, our funders, board members and staff—who are helping us to achieve our goals and objectives. We look forward to working with you again in 2025.

RIMA KUPRYTÉ, DIRECTOR OF EIFL

TRANSFORMING PUBLIC LIBRARIES IN UGANDA

EIFL partnership with the National Library of Uganda accelerates digital inclusion

Photo by Jjumba Martin for EIFL

“With EIFL, we have come a long way in building the ICT capacity of public and community libraries and connecting communities in Uganda. Our libraries across the country are now recognized as key local contributors to development and digital inclusion.”

– ADONIA KATUNGISA, DIRECTOR, NATIONAL LIBRARY OF UGANDA

In 2010, an EIFL study of perceptions of public libraries in Uganda found that most people saw libraries as places for storing information, quiet reading and study. Very few public or community libraries had computers or internet connections for public use and librarians’ digital skills were limited.

Today the picture is very different. Equipped with digital technology, and staffed by librarians with digital information and training skills, public and community libraries are playing a vital role in digital inclusion, especially in under-resourced rural and peri-urban areas. Providing free or affordable access to ICT and digital literacy training are now recognised as essential public library services that are attracting thousands of people from all walks of life— farmers, students and their teachers, vulnerable and unemployed women and youth, health workers, police and government officials.

This transformation has been remarkable, and EIFL is proud to have played a part in it.

CHANGING PERCEPTIONS OF PUBLIC LIBRARIES

Communities across Uganda are served by over 150 public and community libraries. The National Library of Uganda (NLU) sets policies, standards and guidelines for these libraries, advocates for resourcing of libraries, and provides training for librarians. From early on the NLU has been our main partner in working with libraries in Uganda.

In 2012, guided by the findings of the EIFL study, ‘Perceptions of Public Libraries in Uganda’, EIFL and the NLU embarked on a strategy to change government and public perceptions of public libraries. The strategy

combined three elements: developing new library services using ICT to serve community needs; building the capacity of librarians to use ICT effectively in services and training, and an advocacy campaign that specifically targeted national government ministries and agencies.

Between 2012 and 2015, EIFL provided small grants to support seven public and community library projects that introduced ICT into services targeting farmers, unemployed young people and rural women. Short case studies based on the projects, showing the impact of ICT-enabled public libraries, have been helpful in changing perceptions of key stakeholders.

Our capacity building initiative, starting in 2014, targeted libraries that already had or that were about to receive computers and internet connections for public use. Our aim was to ensure that librarians were ready to use their new equipment effectively, and the training curriculum included basic and advanced ICT skills for librarians, new service development and management skills, and training and facilitation skills.

EIFL and the NLU used mounting evidence of the positive impact of ICT in public and community library services in advocacy at the national level to improve resourcing of libraries. Over time, this worked, and doors began to open. In 2018 the Uganda Communications Commission (UCC), the government agency mandated to develop a modern communications sector in Uganda and to expand rural communications, agreed to support a small pilot project that involved equipping three public and community libraries with computers and internet connections for public use.

The pilot project, with Pallisa Public Library in Eastern Region, Hoima Public Library in Western Region and Nakaseke Community Library in Central Region, was a success. It led to the formal inclusion of public and community libraries in annual ICT roll-outs funded by the Uganda Communications Universal Service and Access Fund (UCUSAF), which is managed by the UCC. In relation to this, EIFL and the NLU committed to ongoing training of librarians at newly-equipped libraries to ensure that the equipment would be integrated into services.

From 2019 onwards, public and community libraries received annual allocations of digital technology from the UCC. By the end of 2024 the UCC had installed packages of digital equipment at 39 public and community libraries, and 30 more libraries have been earmarked for the UCC’s roll-out in 2025. The UCC equipment packages are comprehensive: each library receives 10 computers, plus wireless internet, a printer, a scanner and a photocopier.

“Over the next five years, the UCC’s strategic plan focuses on enhancing ICT infrastructure in approximately 100 public and community libraries. We believe this will help bring ICT access to underserved and vulnerable communities, including the elderly, people with disabilities, and low-income populations. We are also very happy to see libraries actively conducting digital skills training for local communities,” said James Beronda, Director of UCUSAF at the UCC.

MAJOR NATIONAL PROJECT

In 2021, EIFL and partners, including the NLU and the Uganda-based NGO Maendeleo Foundation, launched a new national project, ‘Digital skills and inclusion through libraries in Uganda’. This project included more libraries that had received equipment from the UCC. It trained librarians from 27 libraries serving urban, peri-urban and rural communities to build digital skills of two especially marginalized groups— women and unemployed youth. Skilled librarians provided training in digital and mobile literacy and introduced trainees to free online learning opportunities.

“We use ICT training to introduce useful online resources such as courses, tutorials and YouTube videos. This allows people to learn new skills and generate income or diversify what their business can offer,” says Peter Balaba, a librarian at Nakaseke Public Library.

In just two years, 50 librarians and library volunteers from the 27 libraries provided digital and mobile information literacy training, covering basic ICT skills, internet searching, digital marketing, Google tools and online safety, to over 22,000 people. Of these, 1,500 enrolled for online courses on topics including entrepreneurship, computer coding and web design, repairing digital equipment, hairdressing and tailoring.

Libraries reported receiving requests for ICT training from government departments, police, health service providers, schools and other local institutions. “The fact that our local authorities value the training programme in the library so highly influences the community to see it as a valuable activity that can help them in future. The leaders do mobilization

in various communities urging people to take part in the training; parents also appreciate the services, and there is a lot of excitement in our community," said Mathew Olowo, Librarian at Bugiri Public Library in Uganda's Eastern Region.

LIBRARIES MAKING A LASTING IMPACT

Public access ICT and training are making a lasting impact in communities. Library trainees are using their new ICT skills to start small businesses, find jobs, get promoted, research the internet for ideas and information, study further and learn new technical and craft-making skills.

Kawempe Youth Centre, Central Region

To improve her performance in ICT at school Natterbo Hadijah joined the digital skills programme at Kawempe Youth Centre during the holidays. "We were supported with digital knowledge and equipped with hands-on computer skills which I later-on applied in my academics and final computer examinations. I am happy and proud that thanks to this training I was able to successfully pass my ICT exam with a distinction."

Kabale Public Library, Western Region

The ICT trainer at Kabale Public Library, Omuntuwabantu Mutahunga Bana, told us that one of their trainees is using skills that he learnt online to repair computer equipment, like screens and mice, and domestic items, like irons. The young man, Martin Kakuru, works part time at a small shop where he generates income by taking in items for repair.

Pallisa Public Library, Eastern Region

Another librarian and trainer, Stella Amuleni from Pallisa Public Library, spoke about 20 keen young potters who completed digital literacy training at the library and researched the internet to find new pot designs and learn new potting methods. "They were used to making just one type of pot. Now they have started to make pots in different shapes and colours."

Koboko Resource Centre, Northern Region

Koboko Resource Centre has helped Brenda to change her life. Brenda left school due to pregnancy in 2020 and her parents could not support her to continue her studies. She enrolled for basic ICT training at her local library and completed the course. Afterwards, Brenda joined a group at the library studying a free online course for a certificate in hair care, make-up, and beauty. "This course changed her life, and she now works in a beauty Salon in Koboko Town, earning a salary," says librarian Peterlee Guma.

A SUSTAINABLE FUTURE

The new energy in public and community libraries has attracted partnerships in the private sector. Absa Bank Uganda, American Tower Corporation (ATC) Uganda, MTN and Airtel Uganda have partnered with NLU by donating computers and internet connectivity to libraries and in some cases renovating and furnishing library buildings to accommodate digital community spaces. ATC Uganda has also included libraries in their Digital Communities programme and engaged librarians to provide ICT training for communities on a regular basis.

"We cannot overestimate the good partnership and strong contribution of the UCC and other development partners, like EIFL, without which we would not have achieved this level of ICT resourcing. Public and community libraries are now recognized as partners in achieving national, regional and international development goals for universal access to information and ICT. And we are attracting new partners and partnerships. This growing network of support strengthens our ability to reach even more people and communities," said Adonia Katungisa, Director of NLU.

Thank you to the Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation and the Wehubit Programme implemented by the Belgian development agency, Enabel, for supporting the work of the EIFL Public Library Innovation Programme in Uganda.

EIFL'S WORK WITH PUBLIC LIBRARIES IN UGANDA —

- 2010** Commissioned research, 'Perceptions of Public Libraries in Uganda'
- 2011** Released findings of 'Perceptions of Public Libraries in Uganda'
- 2012** Awarded grants to seven public and community libraries to develop ICT-based community information services to meet the needs of farmers, health workers and young job seekers in their communities
Advocacy campaign for government investment in library ICT
- 2014** Launched capacity building initiative for 22 public and community libraries
- 2016** EIFL and the National Library of Uganda (NLU) sign MoU to collaborate on public library modernization and ongoing training of librarians at newly-equipped libraries
- 2018** Uganda Communications Commission (UCC) agrees to provide digital technology to three public libraries, as a pilot project
- 2019** Four NLU staff members complete EIFL train-the-trainers programme and are involved in continuing professional development of librarians

Formal inclusion of public and community libraries in UCC's Uganda Communications Universal Service and Access Fund (UCUSAF) Phase III programmes

UCC equips 11 more public and community libraries

2020/2022 UCC equips 18 more public and community libraries

2021/2023 With partners implemented a national library project focused on digital literacy for women and unemployed youth. The project trained 50 librarians and library volunteers to provide ICT training in their communities. 27 public and community libraries provided digital skills training to 22,000 people; 1,500 people completed online courses, learning skills that would change their lives

2024 UCC equips 10 more public and community libraries

UCC earmarks 30 more libraries for 2025 digital technology roll-out

EIFL maintains a virtual peer-learning network of public library trainers from Ghana, Kenya, Namibia, Uganda and Zambia

ORIENT
EXPRESS

MEET THE PEOPLE

Using knowledge to change their
lives and the lives of others

Photo by Chetan Singh Gill

BLESSINGS KATUMA

ASSISTANT LIBRARIAN & TECHNOLOGY AND INNOVATION CENTRE COORDINATOR, UNIVERSITY OF MALAWI MALAWI

In 2024, EIFL's partner consortium, the Malawi Library and Information Consortium (MALICO), approached EIFL requesting an information session for librarians on copyright and access to knowledge in Malawi.

"Copyright laws can significantly impact our work as librarians, and we were seeking EIFL's support in reviewing Malawi's Copyright Act of 2016, specifically focusing on how it affects libraries," says Blessings Katuma, who was nominated by MALICO to serve as EIFL Copyright Coordinator for Malawi.

"As librarians, we were finding that some aspects of the law were hindering our work.

"For example, Section 48 that deals with permitted uses by libraries is complex and difficult to understand, even for copyright specialists. The making of digital copies for our researchers is barred, and before we can make an accessible format copy for a student with a visual impairment, first we must check if the item is commercially available, that delays or even prevents access."

The EIFL information session was extremely useful, says Blessings. A representative from the Copyright Society of Malawi (COSOMA) attended the session during which participants assessed the Copyright Act from the library point of view, and reviewed recommendations by EIFL for improvements.

"We will be writing to COSOMA outlining the suggested amendments and asking for the inclusion of librarians in the law reform processes that are currently underway. It is essential for librarians' voices to be heard to ensure that our copyright system maximizes opportunities for education and research."

"EIFL's copyright programme has been instrumental in supporting library advocacy for copyright amendments in many countries, and we wanted to tap their practical expertise."

– BLESSINGS KATUMA

MOJCA KOTAR

ASSISTANT SECRETARY GENERAL, UNIVERSITY OFFICE FOR LIBRARY ACTIVITIES AT THE RECTORATE OF THE UNIVERSITY OF LJUBLJANA SLOVENIA

EIFL has played a crucial role in building strong foundations for open science in Slovenia, says Mojca Kotar.

“Since 2009, we have drawn extensively on EIFL’s expertise in developing open access and open science infrastructures and policies, and today, open access and open science are driving reform in our higher education and research institutions. Iryna Kuchma (EIFL Open Access Programme Manager), is extremely knowledgeable about the European Commission’s (EC’s) mandatory requirements for open science.

“We therefore always ask Iryna to read and comment on draft legislation that is in public consultation, and she has worked closely with government teams to help ensure that our national laws and strategies on scientific research are fully aligned with the EC’s requirements,” says Mojca.

National laws and policies— like the Scientific Research and Innovation Activities Act (2022) and the Decree on performing research activities according to the principles of open science (2023)— are shaping institutional policies. “For example,” says Mojca, “the Slovenian Quality Assurance Agency introduced compliance with open science principles as one of the minimal standards for tenures and promotions at higher education and research institutions, and in 2024 the University of Ljubljana included principles of open science as one of the requirements for recipients of stable funding of scientific research activities.”

To keep up with developments, researchers need training, and Mojca and her team provide training at the University of Ljubljana. “When planning, we always check EIFL’s Digital Research Literacy Training Programme Outline for Librarians and EIFL’s other guides for open science training.” Mojca also participates in EIFL’s monthly online meet-ups of open science trainers. “These meet-ups are really enriching. Trainers from EIFL’s global network share experiences. It is good to know we are not alone in facing issues.”

“EIFL has supported Slovenia throughout our open science and responsible research assessment journeys on the national and institutional levels, which laid the foundation for all the current legislation and policies being adopted now.”

– MOJCA KOTAR

MARIKA ZHORZHOLIANI

HEAD OF THE DEPARTMENT, TSU NATIONAL SCIENCE LIBRARY GEORGIA

The Georgian Integrated Library Information System Consortium (GILISC) joined EIFL in 2000 and is one of our oldest partners. In 2017 the consortium changed its name to GILISC 2017. TSU (‘Ivane Javakhsishvili’ Tbilisi State University) National Science Library plays a leading role in the consortium and GILISC members nominated Marika Zhorzholiani to serve as EIFL Licensing Coordinator for Georgia in 2017.

“Back in 2017 the consortium had just 30 member universities. Today, we have 42 universities that are members. The main reason for the increase is the free or discounted access to commercial e-resources that EIFL negotiates for its library consortium partners and their members,” says Marika.

GILISC 2017 currently subscribes to six discounted and 11 free e-resources that are available through EIFL to partner countries, including e-journals, e-book collections and databases. Libraries actively sign up for licenses for every e-resource that is made available to them. “We raise member libraries’ awareness about these e-resources, and we train librarians to ensure that scholars and researchers know how to access and use them. They are well used, with just under 114,000 full-text article downloads in 2024, almost three times as many as in 2023.”

GILISC 2017 also raises awareness among member institutions about the EIFL-negotiated discount for services that provide remote access to licensed e-resources. “It is very important for academics, researchers and students to be able to access e-resources from anywhere, at any time and we are slowly convincing libraries to introduce remote access services,” says Marika.

“Our other task is to encourage Georgian authors to publish more in open access and benefit from EIFL-negotiated agreements with publishers offering waived or discounted Article Processing Charges (APCs). With EIFL’s support we are also advancing open access repositories and journals in Georgia.”

“EIFL’s approach in working with library consortia has really helped us to see the benefits of working together to serve our academic communities and sharing with them the latest developments in scholarly communications.”

– MARIKA ZHORZHOLIANI

ANGELA AKUA BOATEMAA

HEADMISTRESS, ST ANTHONY'S R/C JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL GHANA

Ashanti Regional Public Library has transformed ICT teaching at St Anthony's R/C Junior High School in Kumasi, capital of Ghana's Ashanti Region, says Headmistress Angela Akua Boatemaa.

"Our ICT teachers were struggling to give the students hands-on experience of digital technology. The average class size is 60 students and the school has just 20 desktop computers. The pressure on the computers was too great to give students enough time to practice, and we did not have internet for the students to use," says Angela.

Librarians from Ashanti Regional Public Library visited the school bringing laptops, tablets and a wifi-internet router to give students practical knowledge and experience of ICT. The training included how to use search engines, assessing and selecting information found online and online safety.

The library is one of 15 regional libraries taking part in the 'Digital Learning @ Ghana Public Libraries project', a partnership between EIFL and the Ghana Library Authority. The project has trained librarians and library ICT coordinators from across the country to provide digital and mobile literacy training to students aged 12 - 18, and to introduce them to free and open online educational resources. In 2024, the libraries visited 105 schools, training almost 7,000 students. They also organized in-depth digital literacy workshops in libraries, attracting over 800 school students.

"The library's classes inspired us to invest in an internet connection for our students because we now know they can work on their own, without supervision. And the students have gained in confidence—they even go to the computer room during break times to practice. This has relieved the pressure on the computers during class times," says Angela.

"The students are more excited about learning ICT. They are using their new online research skills to complete their homework and they are learning about the wider world, and communities outside Ghana."

— ANGELA AKUA BOATEMAA

OUR NETWORK

EIFL partner library consortia nominate coordinators who serve as the main point of contact between EIFL's Programmes and their consortium. In their countries, they lead and facilitate activities initiated by EIFL, and have been central to our success and achievements over the years.

Thank you to all our Country Coordinators, Licensing Coordinators, Open Access Coordinators and Copyright Coordinators for their enthusiasm and hard work in 2024.

ALBANIA

Consortium of Albanian Libraries

Country Coordinator: Albana Velianj
Licensing Coordinators: Renata Bardhi and Mirlona Buzo
Open Access Coordinator: Renata Bardhi

ARMENIA

Digital Library Association of Armenia (DLAA)

Country Coordinator: Anna Chulyan
Licensing Coordinators: Tatevik Tamazyan
Copyright Coordinator: Hasmik Galstyan
Open Access Coordinator: Tigran Zakaryan

AZERBAIJAN

Azerbaijan Library & Information Consortium for Availability of Electronic Information (AzLIC)

Country & Licensing Coordinators: Jamila Yusifova and Iltifat Ibrahimov
Copyright Coordinator: Adila Abdullayeva

BOTSWANA

Botswana Libraries Consortium (BLC)

Country & Licensing: Coordinator: Naniki Maphakwane
Copyright Coordinator: Khutsafalo Kadimo
Open Access Coordinator: Poloko Ntokwane

CHINA

Library Network of the Chinese Academy of Sciences

Country Coordinator: Xiwen Liu
Open Access & Copyright Coordinator: Kunhua Zhao

CONGO

Consortium des Bibliothèques Académiques du Congo (COBAC)

Country Coordinator: Eliezer Mwangane
Licensing Coordinator: Jean Baptiste Unen

CÔTE D'IVOIRE

Consortium des Bibliothèques de l'Enseignement Supérieur de Côte d'Ivoire (COBES-CI)

Country & Licensing Coordinator: Cécile Coulibaly
Copyright Coordinator: Ahou Marie-Claire Allou Ouffouet
Open Access Coordinator: Adjoh Hortense Kakpo Epse Outtara

ESTONIA

Consortium of Estonian Libraries Network (ELNET)

Country & Licensing Coordinator: Marika Meltsas
Copyright Coordinator: Karmen Linask
Open Access Coordinator: Elena Sipria-Mironov

ETHIOPIA

Consortium of Ethiopian Academic and Research Libraries (CEARL)

Country Coordinator: Girma Aweke
Licensing Coordinators: Bedassa Motuma Beyene
Copyright Coordinator: Ato Yoseph Bizuneh
Open Access Coordinator: Getnet Lemma

FIJI

Fiji Library Consortium

Country & Licensing Coordinator: Udyia Shukla

GEORGIA

Georgian Integrated Library Information System Consortium (GILISC) 2017

Country, Open Access & Copyright Coordinator: Nino Pavliashvili
Licensing Coordinator: Marika Zhorzholiani

GHANA

Consortium of Academic and Research Libraries in Ghana (CARLIGH)

Country Coordinator: Richard Bruce Lamptey
Licensing Coordinator: Mac Anthony Cobblah
Copyright Coordinator: Teresa Adu
Open Access Coordinators: Donyina Fokuo and Nana Tuhufo Quagraine

KENYA

Kenya Libraries and Information Services Consortium (KLISC)

Country & Licensing Coordinator: Arnold Mwanzu
Copyright Coordinator: Paul Gichohi
Open Access Coordinator: Stanislaus Agava

KOSOVO

Consortium of Electronic Libraries in Kosovo (CELK)

Country, Licensing & Open Access Coordinator: Bukurije Haliti

KYRGYZSTAN

Kyrgyzstan Library Information Consortium (KLIC)

Country Coordinator: Jyldyz Bekbalaeva
Licensing, Copyright & Open Access Coordinator: Tolgonai Kozhokanova

LAOS

Laos Library and Information Consortium (LALIC)

Country, Copyright & Licensing Coordinator: Sypha Phongsavath
Open Access Coordinator: Sisavanh Linsavath

LATVIA

National Library of Latvia

Country, Licensing & Open Access Coordinator: Ilze Linde
Copyright Coordinator: Inta Mikluna

LESOTHO

Lesotho Library Consortium (LELICO)

Country Coordinator: Buhle Mbambo-Thata
Copyright Coordinator: Pontso Nkuebe
Licensing Coordinator: Tahleho Tseole
Open Access Coordinator: Matseliso Kabeli

LITHUANIA

Lithuanian Research Library Consortium (LMBA)

Country & Licensing Coordinator: Jevgenija Sevcova
Copyright Coordinator: Janina Marcinkeviciene
Open Access Coordinator: Gintare Tautkeviciene

MALAWI

Malawi Library and Information Consortium (MALICO)

Country Coordinator: Patrick Mapulanga
Licensing Coordinator: Trevor Namondwe
Copyright Coordinator: Blessings Katuma
Open Access Coordinator: Chifundo Chipendo

MALDIVES

(No name — under development)

Country Coordinator: Zulhana Adam
Licensing Coordinator: Majidha Ali

MOLDOVA

Electronic Resources for Moldova (REM)

Country & Licensing Coordinator: Elena Tudor Railean

Copyright Coordinator: Mariana Harjevschi

Open Access Coordinator: Natalia Cheradi

NAMIBIA

Namibia Library Consortium (NALICO)

Country Coordinator: Victoria Isaacks (until May), Hedwich Meyer (from May)

Licensing Coordinator: Namutenya Hamwaalwa

Copyright Coordinator: Victoria Isaacks

NEPAL

Nepal Library and Information Consortium (NeLIC)

Country, Licensing & Open Access Coordinator: Jagadish Aryal

NORTH MACEDONIA

Macedonian e-Libraries (MEL)

Country, Licensing, Copyright & Open Access Coordinator: Miodrag Dadasovic

PALESTINE

Palestinian Library and Information Consortium (PALICO)

Country Coordinators: Diana Sayej Naser; Rami Alhindawi for Gaza

Licensing Coordinator: Mohammad Abu Hamdieh

Open Access Coordinator: Asad Tom

SENEGAL

Consortium des Bibliothèques de l'Enseignement Supérieur du Sénégal (COBESS)

Country & Licensing Coordinator: Mandiaye Ndiaye

Copyright Coordinator: Awa Diouf Cisse

Open Access Coordinators: Djibril Diallo, Abdoulaye Gueye and Mangaty Sakho

SERBIA

Serbian Library Consortium for Coordinated Acquisition (KoBSON)

Country Coordinator: Tatjana Timotijevic

Licensing Coordinators: Tatjana Timotijevic and Boris Denadic

Copyright Coordinator: Dragana Milunovic

Open Access Coordinator: Milica Sevkusic

SLOVENIA

Consortium of Slovene Electronic Collections (COSEC)

Country Coordinator: Karmen Stular Sotosek

Licensing Coordinator: Herman Erculj

Open Access Coordinator: Alenka Kavcic-Colic

SUDAN

Sudanese Academic Libraries Consortium (SALC)

Country Coordinator: Iman Abdelrahman

Licensing Coordinator: Babelshafia Makki (until September), Entsar Abbas Ebraheem Mohamed (from September)

Copyright & Licensing Coordinator: Wahbi Abdalrahman (from September)

Open Access Coordinator: Rania M. Hassan Baleela (until September), Babelshafia Makki (from September)

TANZANIA

Consortium of Tanzania Universities and Research Libraries (COTUL)

Country & Open Access Coordinator: Paul Samwel Muneja

Licensing Coordinator: Cyrill Ndekakao

THAILAND

Electronic Information for Libraries in Thailand (eifl-Thailand)

Country, Copyright and Licensing Coordinator:

Soeythip Sukul

Open Access Coordinator: Adisak Sukul

UGANDA

Consortium of Uganda University Libraries (CUUL)

Country Coordinator: David Bukenya

Licensing Coordinator: Drake Tamale (until July), Florence Nambooze (from July)

Copyright Coordinator: Eric Haumba (until July),

Bosco Apparatus Buruga (from July)

Open Access Coordinator: Hassan Ssenooba (until July), Drake Tamale (from July)

UKRAINE

Association 'Informatio-Consortium'

Country, Copyright, Licensing & Open Access Coordinator: Oleksii Vasyliev

UZBEKISTAN

EIFL Uzbekistan Consortium

Country Coordinator: Husniya Boysunova

Licensing Coordinator: Alisher Kattabekov

Open Access Coordinator: Gulbakhor Kabiljanova

ZAMBIA

Zambia Library Consortium (ZALICO)

Country & Licensing Coordinator: Eness Chitumbo

Copyright Coordinator: Benson Njobvu

Open Access Coordinator: Pilate Chewe

ZIMBABWE

Zimbabwe University Libraries Consortium (ZULC)

Country & Licensing Coordinator: Sarlomie Zinyemba

Copyright Coordinator: Rosemary Maturure

Open Access Coordinator: Blessing

Chiparausha

OUR TEAM

The EIFL General Assembly (GA) 2024 took place in Istanbul, Turkey, from 7 - 9 October.

STAFF

Andrius Kriščiūnas, Finance Manager

Britt-Marie Wideberg, Licensing Programme Manager (from April)

Edvaldas Baltrūnas, Public Library Innovation Programme Coordinator

Iryna Kuchma, Open Access Programme Manager

Jean Fairbairn, Communications Manager, Website and Publications

Jevgenija Ševcova, Programmes and Events Coordinator

Louise Stoddard, Communications Manager (until February)

Milica Ševkušić, Open Access Programme, Project Coordinator

Ramunė Petuchovaitė, Public Library Innovation Programme Manager

Rima Kuprytė, Director

Teresa Hackett, Copyright and Libraries Programme Manager

Ugnė Lipeikaitė, Public Library Innovation Programme Impact Manager

MANAGEMENT BOARD

Emilija Banionytė, Chairperson, Vilnius County Adomas Mickevičius Public Library, Lithuania

Adam Hyde, Founder of Coko, Book Sprints, Paged.js, Open Publishing Awards and the Open Publishing Fest (until October)

Colleen Campbell, Max Planck Digital Library, Max Planck Society, Germany

David Bukenya, Uganda Christian University

Jyldyz Bekbalaeva, American University of Central Asia, Kyrgyzstan

Marjan Vernooy-Gerritsen, retired, former Programme Manager for IT & Research at SURF, The Netherlands (from October)

FINANCIAL REPORT

EIFL FINANCES 2024

INCOME	€	%
• Programme income	713,144	22.7%
• Participation fees	61,441	2.0%
• General Support Funds and Reserves	2,328,415	74.2%
• Sponsorship, interest and other income	37,135	1.1%
Total	3,140,135	

EXPENDITURE	€	%
• Programme delivery	1,022,476	90.9%
• Personnel & contracted expenses	65,479	5.8%
• Operating expenses	36,867	3.3%
Total	1,124,822	

COMMITTED EXPENDITURE FOR 2025–2027 PROGRAMME DELIVERY GENERAL SUPPORT FUNDS AND RESERVES	2,015,313
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OUR FUNDERS

ORGANIZATIONS

We would like to thank the following organizations for their generous support for our work in 2024:

- Arcadia Fund through the American University / Washington College of Law, and the Creative Commons Corporation
- Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation
- European Commission Erasmus+ Programme through Lviv Polytechnic National University, Ukraine
- European Commission Horizon 2020 Framework Programme through OpenAIRE AMKE
- European Commission Horizon Europe Framework Programme (HORIZON)
- Internet Society Foundation through TechSoup Global
- Open Society Foundations
- University of Luxembourg (UNILU) / Luxembourg Development Cooperation Agency (LuxDev)
- Wellcome Trust

EVENTS

In 2024, EIFL organized, supported or took part in 120 events, workshops and conferences about issues that affect access to knowledge.

JANUARY

- Webinar: Integrating ORCID in repositories and CRIS systems
- EIFL-PLIP T-break: Online Safety Training for Youth
- Webinar: COUNTER Release 5.1
- SCOIR project Advisory Board Meeting
- ISOC Regional kick-off meeting
- Open4UA project kick-off meeting
- WSIS +20 briefing
- Knowledge Rights 21 webinar: New Legislative Developments in support of Open Science— Bulgaria and Slovenia

FEBRUARY

- Knowledge Rights 21 webinar: Normalising Open Norms?
- EC Expert Meeting on Framework Conditions for Cooperation with China in Science, Technology and Innovation: 'Open Science, Research Ethics and Integrity and Gender Equality in Research and Innovation'
- Webinar: Towards Diamond Open Access in Western Balkans
- EC event: 'Improving access to and reuse of R&I results, publications and data for scientific purposes'
- Open science trainers meet-up: EIFL resources for open science trainers

MARCH

- Webinar: Open access scholarly publishing in Bosnia and Herzegovina, Croatia, Kosovo, Montenegro, North Macedonia, Serbia and Slovenia

- EIFL-PLIP T-break: Inclusive Library Services
- COMMUNIA conference: Unlocking Knowledge
- Workshop: 'How to get started with the implementation of Open Science nationally'
- 'Digital learning @ Ghana public libraries' Project Stakeholder Forum
- Train-the-trainers workshop for Ghana public libraries
- Workshop: 'Legislating Open Science— A Pathway to Research Transformation'
- Open Access Summit
- Open Climate Campaign partner meeting

APRIL

- Webinar: The impact of Plan S
- Malawi public library stakeholder meetings
- Zambia public library stakeholder meetings
- Internet Society Foundation: SCILLS-funded projects regional meeting
- The Promise and Practice of Open Science— Asia OA meeting
- AJOL webinar: What is Diamond Open Access?
- Webinar: Digital Tools for the Epigraphist
- Train-the-trainers workshop for Ghana public libraries
- International Scientific Conference: Scientific and Publishing Integrity in Biomedicine

MAY

- Open science trainers meet-up: New training resources and activities

- Q&A 1st session— EIFL Grant call: Strengthening no-fee open access publishing in Africa
- 2nd International Conference: Materials and Technologies in Engineering, MTI 2024
- Webinar: Nigeria— the best copyright law in the world?
- 4th KLISC International Conference
- Q&A 2nd session— EIFL Grant call: Strengthening no-fee open access publishing in Africa
- WSIS +20 Forum
- Webinar: No-fee Open Access Publishing in Africa
- Workshop: Building a cohort of open scholarship trainers
- Q&A 3rd session— EIFL Grant call: Strengthening no-fee open access publishing in Africa
- Webinar: DIAMAS Conversation: Advancing Diamond OA in Europe

JUNE

- Q&A 4th session— EIFL Grant call: Strengthening no-fee open access publishing in Africa
- Open science trainers meet-up: New training resources and activities
- COAR Annual Conference 2024
- Webinar: How to get more content for your repository
- Q&A 5th session— EIFL Grant call: Strengthening no-fee open access publishing in Africa

- UXLibs8 Workshop and Conference 2024
- Webinar: Rights Retention and Secondary Publishing Rights
- Annual training event for university libraries in Kyrgyzstan

JULY

- Webinar: Copyright and Access to Knowledge in Malawi: Issues and developments
- Open science trainers meet-up: New training resources and activities
- UN High-Level Political Forum on Sustainable Development Virtual Side Event
- EIFL-PLIP T-break: Digital Reading
- Technology and Innovation Class of the Global Librarianship course at North Carolina Central University, USA

AUGUST

- Webinar: Developing Research Data Management policies
- AfricArXiv Webinar: Diamond Open Access Publishing in Africa
- Train-the-trainers workshop for Ghana public libraries
- Open science trainers meet-up: Research assessment
- 58th Asia Pacific Advanced Network Meeting

SEPTEMBER

- 5th OpenAIRE Train-the-Trainer Bootcamp
- Metropolitan Technical University in Chile Webinar: Public libraries as a driver for social innovation

- 1st PUBMET Summer School on Scholarly Communication
- PUBMET 2024
- Summer school at Sumy State University, Ukraine: 'Open science in education and research: The best EU practices'
- Webinar: Libraries, Copyright and AI for science and research
- Open science trainers meet-up: Reproducibility; Open data
- Portuguese 2024 Open Science Train-the-Trainers Bootcamp
- Webinar: DIAMAS Conversation: Standards and Tools to Elevate Diamond OA Publishing
- Webinar: Libraries, Copyright and the Commons
- SPOZNAJ project training for data experts
- SUPRR discussions: Open access book publishing: University Presses

OCTOBER

- EURAXESS ASEAN Webinar: The Future of Research: An Introduction to Open Science
- EIFL-PLIP T-break: Mobile Literacy Skills for Youth
- COMMUNIA Policy Launch: Why Europe needs a Digital Knowledge Act
- SUPRR discussions: Open access book publishing: Commercial and Non-Commercial Presses
- Train-the-trainers workshop for Ghana public libraries
- 2024 EIFL General Assembly
- The 3rd ICIL Africa 2024 conference
- Annual meeting of Latvian Library Consortium
- Conference: Research in Biomedicine and Health: Quality, Excellence, and Performance

- Webinar: Libraries, Copyright, Research and Development
- Open Access Week 2024
- 3rd Annual Forum for Open Research in MENA
- OA Week 2024 event, Kaunas University of Technology in Lithuania
- OA Week 2024 event, Midlands State University, Gweru, Zimbabwe
- Webinar: What's fair in copyright? Fair use, fair dealing and fair practice
- SUPRR discussions: Open access book publishing: Infrastructure solutions and reflections
- SCOIR project: Unharnessing open research in Ireland
- OA Week 2024 event, Rosebank College, Cape Town, South Africa
- Webinar: Strength through collaboration in Diamond Open Access publishing
- III International Conference Open Science and Innovation in Ukraine 2024
- OA Week 2024 event, African University Library, Mutare, Zimbabwe
- Presentation of the DIAMAS project for journal editors and staff of the publishing unit at the University of Banja Luka
- Conference: Open Science and Intellectual Property Protection
- LIBSENSE webinar: Open Access Publishing in Africa
- Open science trainers meet-up: Creative Commons licences; Research software
- Workshop: Open Journal Systems: Experiences and Recommendations

NOVEMBER

- Open Science Day V in Serbia
- Webinar: Thoth open metadata management and dissemination platform for open access books 50
- Webinar for Asia: Paper Pledge for the Planet campaign
- E-Library training for Laos law faculty
- Webinar for Africa & Europe: Paper Pledge for the Planet campaign
- Webinar for North & South America: Paper Pledge for the Planet campaign
- DIAMAS project meeting: Creating actionable recommendations and guidelines for Diamond OA publishing
- BEAMING project Open Science Clustering Event
- Open access and open science webinar for Fiji Library Consortium
- UKSG November Conference 2024
- iREAL Symposium
- Ukrainian Open Science Forum
- Open science trainers meet-up: Research software; Promoting OA and open science
- IFLA Workshop: Strong and Sustainable Library Fields in Latin America and the Caribbean
- Webinar: How to publish with Oxford University Press journals
- Oxford University Press Online products presentation
- Regional Symposium on Democratizing Science in the Arab region

DECEMBER

- 6th OpenAIRE Train-the-Trainer Bootcamp
- Workshop: Ethical research and publishing, mastering the JSDP journal platform and editorial workflow
- EIFL-PLIP T-break: Graphic Design with Canva for Youth
- 2nd Global Summit on Diamond Open Access
- Conference: 'Integrity, Open Science and Artificial Intelligence in Academia and Beyond: Meeting at the Crossroads'

KEY

- Training, workshops and events organized and/or supported by EIFL
- Presentations given by EIFL staff or partners
- Conferences and events attended by EIFL staff

OUR PARTNERS

EIFL has built relationships with a wide range of organizations to make knowledge more accessible. In 2024, we worked with the following partners:

- Access to Knowledge (A2K) Coalition
- African Journals Online (AJOL)
- African Library and Information Associations and Institutions (AFLIA)
- American University Washington College of Law, Program on Information Justice and Intellectual Property (PIJIP)
- Arab States Research and Education Network (ASREN)
- Association of Lithuanian Municipal Public Libraries
- Citizen's Services & Libraries, City of Aarhus, Denmark
- Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA)
- Coalition Publi.ca
- cOAlition S
- Coko Foundation
- COMMUNIA Association
- Confederation of Open Access Repositories (COAR)
- Copyright for Creativity
- Creative Commons
- Crossref
- DataCite
- Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ)
- DSpace Community Advisory Team (DCAT), Lyris
- Education International
- European Union Intellectual Property Office
- Fundación Karisma
- GÉANT
- Ghana Library Authority
- Global Sustainability Coalition for Open Science Services (SCOSS)
- Google Scholar
- Harvard Open Access Project (HOAP)
- HIFA2020: Healthcare Information For All by 2020
- Information Power
- International Coalition of Library Consortia (ICOLC)
- International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions (IFLA)
- International Union for Conservation of Nature
- Kenya National Library Service
- Knowledge Rights 21
- LIBER
- Library Copyright Alliance (LCA)
- LIBSENSE
- Lithuanian Audiosensory Library
- Maendeleo Foundation
- Namibia Library and Archives Service
- National Institute of Informatics of Japan
- National Library of Uganda
- National Library Service of Malawi
- Networked Digital Library of Theses and Dissertations (NDLTD)
- Nigerian Copyright Commission
- North Carolina Central University, USA
- Open Access Scholarly Publishing Association (OASPA)
- OA Switchboard
- OpenAIRE AMKE
- Open Data and Intellectual Property Institute (ODIPI)
- Open Society University Network (OSUN)
- OA2020
- Public Knowledge Project (PKP)
- ReCreate South Africa
- Research Organization Registry (ROR)
- Soronko Academy
- South Centre
- SPARC
- SPARC Europe
- Tangible Africa / Leva Foundation
- TechSoup
- Trinity College Dublin, Ireland
- UbuntuNet Alliance
- UKSG
- UNESCO
- University of Washington, Information School, USA
- West and Central African Research and Education Network (WACREN)
- Wildlife Conservation Society
- World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO)
- Zambia Library Service

In addition, EIFL collaborated with 81 partners through European Commission-funded projects: Developing Institutional Open Access Publishing Models to Advance Scholarly Communication (DIAMAS); European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Future; Open Practices, Transparency and Integrity for Modern Academia (OPTIMA) and Open Science for Ukrainian Higher Education System (Open4UA).

KEY

- EIFL is a founding member/signatory
- EIFL is a member
- EIFL staff are board or committee members
- Official relations (including MoU)
- Working Relationship

WHERE WE WORK

In 2024, EIFL worked in partnership with library consortia in 37 countries. We have also run projects in an additional 19 countries where we do not have library consortia.

- **PARTNER COUNTRIES** are countries where we have a formal agreement with the national library consortium. EIFL partner consortia work with all EIFL programmes.
- **PROJECT COUNTRIES** are countries in which we have worked with libraries on specific projects.

STAY CONNECTED

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[eifl-net](https://www.linkedin.com/company/eifl-net)

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Tel: +370 5 2080409 **Email:** info@eifl.net

For more information about EIFL and our work visit [eifl.net](https://www.eifl.net)